

ANALYSIS OF TERMS AND CONCEPTS "ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT", "DIGITAL INTERACTION OF PUBLIC AUTHORITIES", "INFORMATION SYSTEMS"

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the terms and concepts of "electronic governance", "digital interaction of public authorities", "information systems". The key approaches of information platforms and international organizations to the definition of the concept of "electronic governance" are summarized. It is found that the term "e-government" was first introduced in 1993 in the US National Performance Review, while the term "e-government" became popular around 1997. E-Government continues to attract the attention of the global community due to its ability to make governments more efficient and effective, thereby transforming the relationship with citizens, businesses and government institutions. It is established that the definition of the concept of digital interaction is connected with a specific aspect or sphere of public administration. It is substantiated that the term "digital interaction of public authorities" has not yet found an agreed scientific interpretation, continues to be analyzed in scientific circles and needs legislative consolidation. The key approaches to defining the concept of "information systems" are systematized. It has been proven that the processes of information exchange are extremely important because they unite this system as an organized set of elements and integrate its capabilities. The need to create effective mechanisms for integrating communicative efforts of government and society in solving common problems is emphasized.

Keywords: electronic governance, digital interaction of public authorities, information systems, public administration.

Formulation of the problem. The problem of communication between the government and society is peculiar and was solved in accordance with the specific historical conditions of the development of society on the basis of two aspects - the political and philosophical vision of the need for such communication and the communicative capabilities of society (instruments of communicative interaction), which technologically corresponded to the level of development of social relations, material and immaterial culture, nature of the political system, etc. With the transition to a digital society, the technological conditions of the communication process have improved significantly, digital technologies have practically eliminated communication barriers that previously existed given the level of technological development of society. Examples of such progress are new trends in public administration, such as electronic government, smart state, state in a smartphone, which determine the technological essence of a new stage of development of public administration processes.

The logic of social transformations in the era of the digital society is determined by the gradual movement towards civilized forms of democracy, which, unlike the era of the crisis of representative democracy, provide for the broad involvement of citizens in the decision-making process.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Issues of the implementation of electronic governance in Ukraine are the subject of research by such specialists, scientists, authors as O. Baranov, S. Dzyuba, I. Klymenko, A. Lysytskyi, A. Semchenko, E. Klepets, Yu. Misnikov, T. Popova, S. Chukut and others. At the same time, it can be noted that a number of specific is-

ssues related to the definition of this and related concepts, as well as the analysis of electronic governance tools and mechanisms, are still at the initial stage of development.

The purpose of this study is to analyze and systematize the conceptual and categorical apparatus in the field of digitalization of public administration ("electronic governance", "digital interaction of public authorities", "information systems").

Presenting main material. Despite 60 years of use, problems related to information and communication technologies in public administration still exist. Statistics from 18 Eurasian countries show a linear relationship between Internet access and frequency of Internet use, and between Internet use and propensity to use private sector services such as Internet banking. However, this does not at all mean an automatic transition to the use of public sector electronic services.

As governments face complex challenges, they are expected to be innovative in the use of resources and the organization of service delivery. Information and communication technologies (ICT) are considered as a factor of change for solving these tasks. Or by improving efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, accountability and/or inclusiveness.

The term "e-government" was first introduced in 1993 in the US National Performance Review, while the term "e-government" became popular around 1997. Nevertheless, ICTs have played an important role in public sector service delivery since the mid-twentieth century.

Table 1 shows the key approaches of information platforms and international organizations to the definition of the concept of "e-government".

Table 1

Approaches to defining the concept of "electronic governance"

Author	Definition content
UNDESA [1]	"Electronic governance" - the use of information and computer technologies and their application by the government to provide information and public services to the population
Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development Glossary of Statistical Terms [2]	The term "e-government" focuses on the use by governments of new information and communication technologies as applied to the full range of government functions. In particular, the network potential offered by the Internet and related technologies has the potential to transform the structures and operations of government
Organization of American States [3]	Electronic government (or e-government) is the application of information and communication technologies to government functions and procedures with the aim of increasing efficiency, transparency and citizen participation
IGI Global platform [4]	Electronic government (e-gov, digital government, online government, or in a certain context transformational government) is the use of Internet technologies as a platform for exchanging information, providing services, and conducting transactions with citizens and businesses and other branches of government. E-government can be used by legislative, judicial or administrative authorities to improve internal efficiency, public service delivery or democratic governance processes
	E-government is the electronic provision of government information and services 24 hours a day, seven days a week
	E-Government is the application of IT to government services and procedures to provide public services and information to citizens, businesses and governments electronically
	Electronic government (e-Gov, digital government, online government, or in some contexts transformational government) refers to the use of Internet technologies as a platform for exchanging information, providing services, and conducting transactions with citizens, businesses, and other branches of government. E-government can be used by legislative, judicial or administrative authorities to improve internal efficiency, public service delivery or democratic governance processes
	Provision of public services online, which makes it possible to expand citizens' access to government, reduce government bureaucracy, expand citizens' participation in democracy, and increase the responsiveness of authorities to citizens' needs
	Electronic government (e-government) is the use of information technologies to provide public services online, which aims to provide faster and better service to interested parties. It can be divided into four main categories namely Government-to-Citizen (G2C), Government-to-Business (G2B), Government-to-Government (G2G) and Government-to-Employee (G2E)

Source: compiled by the author

Communication in the conditions of digital social transformations is one of the most important tools of public management in view of the technologization of society and social relations within it. It is especially important for us to consider the essence of this process in the context of the interaction "public authorities - self-governing organizations".

Analyzing the legal and managerial aspects of public policy in the sphere of interaction between civil society and executive power, it can be determined that civil society as a self-governing institution performs a transformative and protective function in preventing threats of authoritarianism. In the author's opinion, the tools for implementing such functions are volunteer, charitable and voluntary movements, and the example of the development of the Ukrainian state in recent years is yet another confirmation of that. In this regard, we emphasize the need to create effective mechanisms for integrating the communicative efforts of the government and society in solving common problems.

Returning to the analysis of terms and concepts, it should be noted that the definition of digital interaction is formed by scientists, based on different approaches.

Some scientists interpret digital interaction as the automated exchange of data between information databases, applications, other computer systems and form a key component in all networked computerized systems [5; 6].

Others understand this concept as a digital environment in which a special software and hardware complex provides direct real-time communication and has a set of appropriate functions and services for communication between consumers and providers (producers) of goods or services [7; 8].

Still others define the concept of digital interaction through the prism of economic characteristics, focusing on the possibility of achieving a high level of efficiency in public management of the economic sphere at the slightest cost [9; 10].

Thus, the definition of the concept of digital interaction is connected with a specific aspect or sphere of public administration. Approaches to defining the concept of "digital interaction" are grouped in Table 2.

Table 2

Approaches to defining the concept of "digital interaction"

Author	Definition content
Stephen O'Connor [5]; Ramya Mohanakrishnan [6]	It is an automated exchange of data between information databases, applications, other computer systems and forms a key component in all networked computerized systems
Baranov O.A. [7]; Michael E. Porter, Victor E. Millar [8]	This is a digital environment in which a special hardware and software complex provides direct communication in real time and has a set of appropriate functions and services for communication between consumers and providers (producers) of goods or services
Oleshko T. I., Kasyanova N.V., Smerichevskyi S. F. [9]; Deanira Laze [10]	The concept of digital interaction is interpreted through the prism of economic characteristics, emphasizing the possibility of achieving a high level of management efficiency at the lowest costs

Source: compiled by the author

At the same time, it is worth noting that the term "digital interaction of public authorities" has not yet found an agreed scientific interpretation, continues to be analyzed in scientific circles and needs legislative consolidation.

Implementation of digital interaction of public authorities is carried out through the use of information systems. Key approaches to defining the concept of "information systems" are listed in Table 3.

Table 3

Approaches to defining the concept of "information systems"

Author	Definition content
Britannica [11]	An integrated set of components for collecting, storing and processing data, as well as for providing information, knowledge and digital products
Emeritus [12]	It is a combination of software, hardware and telecommunication networks to collect useful data, especially in an organization
Master's in Data Science [13]	It is a network used to collect, store, process, analyze and distribute data
Collat school of business [14]	It is a general term used to describe the various networks, hardware and software used by people and businesses to make sense of data and use it. In addition to interpreting data, information systems also collect, process, and disseminate this data
Information Technology Laboratory [15]	A discrete collection of information resources, organized for the collection, processing, storage, use, replenishment, distribution and destruction of information
Technopedia [16]	It is a collection of several pieces of equipment involved in the collection, processing, storage and dissemination of information

Source: compiled by the author

It is obvious that the lack of communication entails an imbalance of the unity of the integral formation of power as an organic phenomenon. Organic, because the current system of power is a rather delicate matter, absolutely sensitive to challenges and threats, and therefore such that it no longer acts as a mechanism, but as a complete system. Such organicity makes the processes of information exchange extremely important, because they unite this system as an organized set of elements and integrate its possibilities.

Conclusions. E-government is often the result of formal and informal interaction of actors, which leads to the emergence of complex relationships that affect the speed of digital development. E-Government continues to attract the attention of the global community due to its ability to make governments more efficient and effective, thereby transforming the relationship with citizens, businesses and government institutions. The conceptual and terminological apparatus is systematized according to the research topic. The conducted analysis made it possible to identify problems that require further scientific investigations and discussions, as well as agreement and legislative consolidation of

certain concepts, in particular, the term "digital interaction of public authorities".

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